

A REVISION OF THREE CONUS TAXA:

C. HALLI, DA MOTTA, 1983, *C. HYAENA* HWASS IN BRUGUIÈRE,
1792, *C. MUTABILIS* REEVE, 1844

by

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When the first batch of what was subsequently described as *C. halli* was received from Peter Hall, the color and pattern variations seen were of such a diversified nature, it was thought that more than one species was involved. When it was confirmed that all specimens were collected from the same locality, it established that we were dealing with a highly polymorphic species. Some resembled *C. concolor* Sowerby, 1834; others, *C. gilvus* Reeve, 1849 but with ample study material, an intergrading series emerged to establish the conspecificity of all the varietal forms, which subsequently showed that the majority was closest to the species popularly known as *C. hyaena*. At the time, the status of *C. hyaena*, as a biological species, was thought to have already been established and generally accepted as occurring in the west coast of India, Sumatra and Bay of Bengal. Walls (1979) discussed and reproduced figures of three specimens (Cone Shell p. 361) which purported to represent this species. The shell is pyriform to some extent with a convex spire and rounded shoulders. There was some similarity to several color forms of *C. halli* but the structural morphology of the two shells was distinctly different. The new discovery is narrower at the shoulder, with flatter sides and a more elongate body whorl.

Continuing to dig into earlier literature, I unearthed the following:

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FIG. A — *C. hyaena* Var. A Hwass in Brug.

FIG. B — *C. hyaena* Var. B Hwass in Brug.

1. A. J. Kohn (1968): Type specimen and identity of the described species CONUS IV. The species identified by Hwass, Bruguière and Olivi in 1792, p. 461:

«The Hwass Collection contains the specimen described for Var. A and illustrated in *Tableau* Pl. 327, Fig. 5, (FIG. A) and by Kiener (1845: Pl. 35, Fig. 4). The specimen (MHN No. 1106/91) measures 61 × 33.5mm and is here selected the lectotype of *C. hyaena* Hwass in Bruguière and is shown in Pl. 5, Fig. 53. There is no specimen of Var. B (FIG. B) at Geneva. Although the nominal species is thus clearly defined, the biological species it represents is problematical and evidently poorly known. It is not listed in faunal accounts of West African *Conus* (Dunker, 1853; Dautzenberg, 1910; Nicklès, 1950; Knudsen, 1956). The type locality is presumably erroneous, and the species is probably of Indo-Malayan occurrence. In the absence of further knowledge, *C. hyaena* Hwass in Bruguière, 1792 is provisionally considered a valid species.»

Diagnosis: *C. hyaena* is only provisionally a valid species of unknown origin because the biological species it represents is problematical and poorly known and therefore cannot be identified.

2. L. C. Kiener (1845) *Iconographie des Coquilles Vivantes*, *C. hyaena* Plate 35, Fig. 4 (a) — translation by John Hall (1968):

«Shell conical, turbinated, with a pointed spire formed of eleven whorls, convex and finely striated on top; separated from each other by a very thin suture. Body whorl marked with superficial striae, of which some of the growth lines are rather evident. There are also grooves, increasing in number toward the base and slightly wavy. Color is yellowish, variegated with narrow axial flames in a tawny color and axial lines of dots or portions of lines in a deeper tawny color. A white band is located slightly below center; interrupted by tawny flames. A similar band is located at the shoulder, but it is rarely completed and is less distinct.»

Length 64mm. Seas of the West Coast of Africa.

This species has much resemblance to *C. namocanus* (= *C. namocanus* Hwass) in that it has the same shape; the only distinguishing feature consists of the wavy axial flames which decorate it.»

Diagnosis: *C. hyaena* is shaped like *C. namocanus*, but can be differentiated by its wavy axial flames of a tawny color, with two white bands, one indistinct. At the time, no known shell fitted this description.

FIG. C

FIG. D

FIG. C — *C. pellis* — *hyaena* Chemnitz, 1795

FIG. D — *C. hyaena* Kiener

3. L. V. Reeve (1843) *Conchologia Iconica*, Vol. I — *C. punctatus* Species 133, Pl. XXIV, Var. B (Figs. 133a & 133c):

«Shell longitudinally streaked with short transverse blackish-brown lines, more or less clouded over.

Conus pellis — hyaenae Chemnitz (*Conch. Cab.* Vol. xi, p. 49, Pl. 181, Fig. 1750 and Fig. 1751 (FIG. C).

Conus hyaena Hwass *Enc. Meth. vers.* vol. i, part 2, p. 656, Pl. 327, Fig. 5 and 7; Lamarck, *Anim. sans vert.* vol. vii, p. 472.

Hab. West Coast of Africa, Coast of Guinea, Dr. Siebold.

There can be no doubt of the complete specific affinity between the two shells described by Chemnitz, Bruguière, Lamarck and others, under the respective titles of *punctatus* (= *bilosus* Roeding, 1798) and *hyaena*. The specimens here selected for representation, though extreme varieties, agree precisely in many important particulars: in the peculiar parallel of the aperture for example, the grooving round the base, the spiral striae of the spire, the slight irregularity of the suture occasioned by the spire being obsoletely coronated, and the pale central band; whilst on the other hand in the features in which they differ, such as the greater or less depression of the spire, and the longitudinal streaks of colouring matter, they are completely assimilated by intermediate varieties.»

(But subsequently in *Supp. Pl. VIII Species 275*, Reeve redescribed *C. hyaena* and remarked: «this, and not the variety of *C. punctatus*, is, according to Kiener, the true *hyaena* of the *Encyclopédie Méthodique*.»)

Diagnosis: Although Reeve at first considered *C. hyaena* and *C. biliosus* conspecific, he subsequently concurred with Kiener's conclusion, and reproduced Kiener's figure under Sp. 275 (FIG. D).

4. J. R. le B. Tomlin (1937) *Catalog of recent & fossil cones:*

«*hyaena* = Bruguière, p. 656, 1792.

W. Africa = *punctatus* Brug. non Gmel (i.e. *piperatus* Dillw.)
f. Reeve.» (= *bilosus* Roeding).

Conclusions: The extent of research at this point allowed for concluding that *C. halli* could be regarded as being morphologically different to the accepted version of *C. hyaena*, or *bilosus* (sometimes confused with *mutabilis*, hence its link with *hyaena*) and since it cannot be confused for any other known

species, *C. halli* could be considered a new and still undescribed species. I accordingly proceeded to propose the taxon as a new species.

Recently, Mr. Claude Vaucher of Museum d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneva very kindly responded to my request and sent me pictures (FIG. E) of the type of *C. hyaena* (No. MHN 1106/91). The resemblance to *C. halli* struck me as being so close, I felt it called for reviewing its entire historical origin.

For FIGS. E, F, see Plate 1.

5. Going back to Walls, he wrote in p. 562 that he considered the closest relatives of *C. hyaena* appear to be *C. biliosus* and *C. lohri* (neither resembles *halli* in any way). However, under «synonym», he remarked: «*Conus mutabilis* of Reeve is the first acceptable use of a name from Chemnitz, since both Reeve and Hwass had the same shell in mind, the oldest available name is *C. hyaena* Hwass, as the *C. «mutabilis»* of Chemnitz is not valid under present-day rules.» (see note *)

FIGS. G — *C. mutabilis* Chemnitz, 1795

FIG. H — *C. mutabilis* Reeve, 1844

* Walls is very much in error. Chemnitz (1730-1800) described many species but his nomenclature was not consistently binominal and the new specific names have no status under ICZN rules. However, Reeve formally redescribed *C. mutabilis* thereby validating the taxon and becomes the author of this now valid species.

6. Reeve's description of *C. mutabilis* is given in Pl. XLV, Species 249, Figs. a, b and c:

«The changeable Cone. Shell turbinated, somewhat pear-shaped, smooth, grooved in a waved manner towards the base; light brown often very pale in the middle, irregularly streaked with brown and encircled with interrupted brown lines; spire convex, spirally striated, sutures rugged and uneven, apex raised.

Chemnitz, Conch. Cab, vol. xi, p. 52, pl. 182, Fig. 1758 and 1759 (FIG. G)

Hab — ?

In my observations on the *Conus vexillum* (Pl. 1, Sp. 3) it is related how Lamarck quotes as a variety of that species a shell figured by Chemnitz under the title of *Conus mutabilis*. These remarks were offered under an apprehension that the figures alluded to could not strictly be referred to the *Conus vexillum* and conclude thus: «It is, however, exceedingly difficult to say what species that figure is intended to represent.» I have now completely identified the *Conus mutabilis* of the 'Conchylian Cabinet' as a very distinct species and have the pleasure of representing specimens of different varieties from the collections of Mrs. Stainforth, Mr. Gray and the British Museum.» (FIG. H)

Diagnosis: Reeve does not link *mutabilis* with *hyaena*, but his mention of Chemnitz's two figures F. 1758 and F. 1759 clearly associates *mutabilis* as the shell which Walls considers is conspecific with *hyaena* as figured in p. 361, (Cone Shells, 1979).

7. G. W. Tryon (1884) Manual of Conchology, vol. vi, cited Conch. Cab. xi, p. 52, pl. 182, F. 1758, F. 1759. (FIG. G).

«MUTABILIS. Shell somewhat swollen above, spire striate, light yellowish brown, variegated by darker strigations and faint revolving lines or rows of spots often indistinctly lighter, banded in the middle. 1.75-2.5 inches. Red Sea, E. Indies, China.

C. hyaena Reeve, not Hwass (Fig. 20) is a synonym.»

And in the Index:

«HYAENA (*Conus*) Hwass

HYAENA (*Conus*) Reeve Icon. Suppl. 275 = *mutabilis* Chem.

HYAENA (*Conus*) Reeve, Conch. Icon. F. 133 = *C. punctatus* Chem.» (= *biliosus* Roeding).

Diagnosis: Tryon associates *C. mutabilis* with Reeve's redescribed *C. hyaena*, in Suppl. VIII, Species 275 without recognizing it as the authentic *hyaena* of Hwass.

8. R. Tucker Abbott & S. Peter Dance (1982), Compendium of Seashells, p. 258, listed a reproduction of:

«Hyaena Cone — *Conus hyaena* Hwass, 1792. India, Bay of Bengal. Tide pools and offshore; common. Syn. *mutabilis* Reeve.»

Diagnosis: The figure shown is not that of Hwass's *hyaena*, but is a typical *C. mutabilis*, as we now know.

Conclusions: It becomes clear that what was considered as *C. hyaena* is, in fact, a distinct and different species: *C. mutabilis* Reeve, 1844.

C. hyaena Hwass in Bruguière, 1792 is what has been recently named: *C. halli* da Motta, 1983 (FIG. F), henceforth to be considered a junior synonym thereof.

I profer my apologies to Peter Hall, but the mistake in not having recognized the authentic *C. hyaena* was due to having been misled by contemporary literature, all too often, unfortunately, published without benefit of any in-depth research. To work on taxonomic roots, there can be no question that examination of the type representing a species under study is absolutely mandatory, and then to link it with an existing population. Had I examined the *hyaena* type (FIG. E) earlier, I would have had reservations about the presentation of *C. hyaena* made by Walls as well as Tucker & Dance and might have avoided proposing «*C. halli*» as a new species. However, I can draw some consolation in having restored the proper identity of *Conus hyaena* and reestablishing the status of *Conus mutabilis* as a separate valid species.

RESUMO

O autor procede a uma revisão exaustiva de três taxa para o género *Conus* (Mollusca: Gastropoda) e conclui que o que tem sido considerado *C. hyaena* é, na verdade, *C. mutabilis* REEVE, 1844; *C. hyaena* HWASS in Bruguière, 1792 é o que foi recentemente descrito como *C. halli* da MOTTA, 1983, sendo este taxon um sinónimo júnior daquele.

fig. 1

fig. 2

fig. 3

fig. E

fig. F

- 1 — *Conus turschi* sp. nov., holotype
 - 2 — *C. turschi* sp. nov., holotype
 - 3 — *C. poehlianus* Sowerby — Rabaul, New Guinea
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- E — *C. hyaena* Hwass, lectotype in M.H.N., Geneva
F — *C. halli* da Motta, homeotype

(Ref. p. 12)

fig. 4

fig. 5

fig. 6

fig. 7

fig. 8

fig. 9

- 4 — *C. turschi* immaculate form
71 × 30.7mm Andaman Sea
- 5 — *C. anceps*
68.9 × 33mm Andaman Sea
- 6 — *C. floccatus*
67.6 × 34.9mm Coral Sea
- 7 — *C. consors*
63.6 × 33.9 Solomon Is.
- 8 — *C. daullei*
60 × 28.5 Great Barrier Reefs
- 9 — *C. circae*
53 × 28.5 Russell Is.